

Studies in *s*-Triazinyl Compounds as Potential Medicinal Agents: Part I

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Several *s*-triazinyl derivatives of 3, 5-dibromo benzocaine have been prepared by the condensation of 2, 4-dichloro-6-(2-phenetidino)-*s*-triazine with 3, 5-dibromo benzocaine in acetone and the product on further reaction with aliphatic, aromatic and heterocyclic amines gave 2-alkyl/aryl/heterocyclyl amino-4-(4-carbethoxy-2, 6-dibromoanilino)-6-(2-phenetidino)-*s*-triazines.

PHENETIDINES and their derivatives have a marked antitubercular, bacteriostatic and anti-pyretic activity¹⁻⁶. Esters of *p*-amino benzoic acid and their halo derivatives are also reported as bacteriostatic, antitubercular and local and general anaesthetics.⁷⁻¹¹ We have prepared *s*-triazine derivatives of the type

s-Triazinyl derivatives possess antibacterial, fungicidal, insecticidal and antimalarial activity.¹²⁻¹⁵

Where R_1 and R_2 are from different alkyl, aryl and heterocyclic amines, to test the antibacterial activity of the new compounds.

Experimental

Preparation of 2-(4-carbethoxy-2, 6-dibromo anilino)-4-(2-phenetidino)-6-chloro *s*-triazine (II) : 3, 5-dibromo-

TABLE I. COMPOUNDS OF THE TYPE (III)

Sr. No.	R_1	R_2	Molecular formula	M.P. °C	Caed % N	Found % N
1.	H	CH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ Br ₂ N ₆ O ₃	350(d)	14.84	15.13
2.	H	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ Br ₂ N ₆ O ₃	135	14.48	14.70
3.	H	<i>n</i> -C ₃ H ₇	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ Br ₂ N ₆ O ₃	315(d)	14.15	14.41
4.	H	<i>n</i> -C ₄ H ₉	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ Br ₂ N ₆ O ₃	190	13.81	14.00
5.	CH ₃	CH ₃	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ Br ₂ N ₆ O ₃	330(d)	14.48	14.30
6.	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ Br ₂ N ₆ O ₃	360(d)	13.81	13.60
7.	<i>n</i> -C ₃ H ₇	<i>n</i> -C ₃ H ₇	C ₂₆ H ₃₂ Br ₂ N ₆ O ₃	290	13.20	13.41
8.	H	HOCH ₂ CH ₂	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ Br ₂ N ₆ O ₄	350(d)	14.09	14.10
9.	HOCH ₂ CH ₂	HOCH ₂ CH ₂	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ Br ₂ N ₆ O ₆	340(d)	13.12	13.00
10.	H	C ₆ H ₅	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ Br ₂ N ₆ O ₃	130	13.38	13.50

TABLE I. COMPOUNDS OF THE TYPE (III) (Contd.)

Sr. No.	R ₁	R ₂	Molecular formula	M.P. °C	Calcd % N	Found % N
11.	H	2-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ Br ₂ ClN ₆ O ₃	94	12.68	13.91
12.	H	3-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ Br ₂ ClN ₆ O ₃	222	12.68	13.90
13.	H	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ Br ₂ ClN ₆ O ₃	200(d)	12.68	12.60
14.	H	2-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₇ H ₂₆ Br ₂ N ₆ O ₃	224	13.08	13.14
15.	H	3-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₇ H ₂₆ Br ₂ N ₆ O ₃	195	13.08	13.25
16.	H	4-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₇ H ₂₆ Br ₂ N ₆ O ₃	245	13.08	13.01
17.	H	2-CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₇ H ₂₆ Br ₂ N ₆ O ₄	111	12.76	12.80
18.	H	4-CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₇ H ₂₆ Br ₂ N ₆ O ₄	257	12.76	12.60
19.	H	2-O ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ Br ₂ N ₇ O ₅	72	14.56	14.30
20.	H	3-O ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ Br ₂ N ₇ O ₅	258	14.56	14.71
21.	H	4-O ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ Br ₂ N ₇ O ₅	95	14.56	14.61
22.	H	2, 5-Cl ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ Br ₂ Cl ₂ N ₆ O ₃	180	12.05	12.11
23.	H	4-Br.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ Br ₃ N ₆ O ₃	268	11.88	11.92
24.	H	2-HO.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ Br ₂ N ₆ O ₄	285	13.04	13.13
25.	H	3-HO.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ Br ₂ N ₆ O ₄	203	13.04	12.94
26.	H	4-HO.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ Br ₂ N ₆ O ₄	250(d)	13.04	13.41
27.	H	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	C ₂₇ H ₂₆ Br ₂ N ₆ O ₃	76	13.08	13.32
28.	H	C ₆ H ₁₀	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ Br ₂ N ₆ O ₃	360(d)	13.27	13.41
29.	H	2-C ₂ H ₅ O.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₈ H ₂₆ Br ₂ N ₆ O ₄	86	12.50	12.46
30.	H	C ₆ H ₅ .CH ₂ CH ₂	C ₂₈ H ₂₆ Br ₂ N ₆ O ₃	350(d)	12.80	13.03
31.	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	C ₂₇ H ₂₆ Br ₂ N ₆ O ₃	145	13.08	13.43
32.	C ₂ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	C ₂₈ H ₂₈ Br ₂ N ₆ O ₃	225	12.80	12.91
33.	H	4-CH ₃ CONH. C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₈ H ₂₇ Br ₂ N ₇ O ₄	219	14.31	14.56
34.	H	4-(1, 3-C ₄ H ₃ N ₂ . HNO ₂ S).C ₆ H ₄	C ₃₀ H ₂₇ Br ₂ N ₉ O ₅ S	296(d)	16.05	16.37
35.	H	$\begin{matrix} \text{NH} \\ \\ 4-(\text{H}_2\text{N}-\text{C}-\text{HNO}_2\text{S}) \\ \\ \text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \end{matrix}$	C ₂₇ H ₂₇ Br ₂ N ₉ O ₅ S	300(d)	16.82	17.14
36.	H	4-(1, 3-C ₃ H ₂ NS. HNO ₂ S).C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₉ H ₂₆ Br ₂ N ₈ O ₅ S ₂	288(d)	14.17	14.05
37.	H	4-(1, 3-C ₄ H ₃ N ₂ .H ₂ .HNO ₂ S).C ₆ H ₄	C ₃₁ H ₂₆ Br ₂ N ₉ O ₅ S	290(d)	15.89	15.67
38.	$\begin{matrix} \text{R}_1 \\ \\ -\text{N} \\ \\ \text{R}_2 \end{matrix}$	= C ₆ H ₅ NO	C ₂₄ H ₂₆ Br ₂ N ₆ O ₄	205	13.87	13.75
39.	$\begin{matrix} \text{R}_1 \\ \\ -\text{N} \\ \\ \text{R}_2 \end{matrix}$	= C ₆ H ₁₀ N	C ₂₅ H ₂₈ Br ₂ N ₆ O ₃	265	13.53	13.81

benzocaine¹⁶ (0.01 mole) was dissolved in acetone and added dropwise during 30 min to a mechanically stirred solution of 2, 4-dichloro-6-*s*-triazine¹⁷ (0.01 mole) in acetone at 35-45°. The

reaction mixture was kept alkaline using NaOH solution (4N) throughout the reaction. The solution was cooled to room temperature after 3 hours and was poured into ice-water. It was made acidic with

dilute HCl (4*N*) solution, stirred and filtered. The product was dried and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 84°-85°.

Found : N 12.61%
 $C_{20}H_{18}Br_2ClN_5O_3$ requires : N 12.23%

Preparation of 2-alkyl/aryl/heterocyclyl amino-4-(4-carbethoxy-2, 6-dibromoanilino)-6(2-phenetidino)-s-triazines (III): 2-(4-carbethoxy-2, 6-dibromoanilino)-4-(2-phenetidino)-6-chloro *s*-triazine (0.001 mole) was taken in dioxane (15 ml) and the amine (0.001 mole) in dioxane (15 ml) was added. The reaction mixture was maintained alkaline with NaOH (4%) solution throughout the reaction. The mixture was refluxed at 60°-70° for 3 hr. It was cooled and poured on ice-water, made acidic with dilute HCl (4*N*) solution, stirred and filtered. The physical and analytical data of these compounds are given in Table I.

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